

Skewed X-Chromosome Inactivation in *EDA*-Related X-Linked Hypohidrotic Ectodermal Dysplasia in a Moroccan Family

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ABSTRACT

X-linked hypohidrotic ectodermal dysplasia (HED) is a rare genetic disorder caused by pathogenic variants in the *EDA* gene and characterized by variable involvement of ectoderm-derived tissues. The aim of this study is to describe the clinical and molecular features of a Moroccan family affected by X-linked HED, with particular emphasis on the role of X-chromosome inactivation in phenotypic variability among female carriers. Clinical and genetic investigations identified the pathogenic *EDA* variant c.467G>A (p.Arg156His) in an affected boy and his heterozygous mother. Notably, the mother exhibited a more severe ectodermal phenotype than typically observed in female carriers. This observation highlights the likely impact of skewed X-chromosome inactivation on disease expression and underscores its importance for genotype–phenotype interpretation, genetic counseling, and multidisciplinary care.

KEYWORDS: X-linked hypohidrotic ectodermal dysplasia; Christ–Siemens–Touraine syndrome; *EDA*; missense variant; skewed X-chromosome inactivation

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I. INTRODUCTION

Ectodermal dysplasias (EDs) constitute a heterogeneous group of rare inherited disorders characterized by abnormal development of tissues derived from the embryonic ectoderm [1]. Among them, X-linked hypohidrotic ectodermal dysplasia (HED), also known as Christ–Siemens–Touraine syndrome, represents the most common and best-characterized form [1]. It is caused by pathogenic variants in the *EDA* gene, located on chromosome Xq12–q13.1 [1,2]. The *EDA* gene encodes ectodysplasin A, which exists mainly as two isoforms, EDA1 and EDA2, interacting respectively with the EDAR and XEDAR receptors [2]. Activation of these receptors triggers the NF- κ B signaling pathway, which plays a crucial role in ectoderm–mesenchyme interactions during embryogenesis and is essential for the normal development of hair, teeth, skin, nails, and exocrine sweat glands [2]. Here, we report the clinical and molecular features of X-linked HED in a Moroccan family, with particular emphasis on the

contribution of X-chromosome inactivation (XCI) to phenotypic variability in a heterozygous female carrier [3].

II. CASE REPORT

The proband was a 6-year-old boy, born to non-consanguineous parents, referred for evaluation of a suspected ectodermal disorder. His medical history was marked by recurrent episodes of otitis media and repeated febrile events, particularly following early childhood vaccinations. Family history revealed ectodermal abnormalities in the mother, including agenesis of four permanent teeth, fine and brittle hair, and nail dystrophy, suggesting an X-linked mode of inheritance. Clinical examination of the child showed typical features of hypohidrotic ectodermal dysplasia, including facial dysmorphism, hypodontia, hypotrichosis, and hypohidrosis, responsible for recurrent episodes of hyperthermia. The skin was dry and scaly, with eczematous lesions involving the external auditory canal. Mild intellectual disability was also

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noted. GENETIC INVESTIGATIONS WERE SUBSEQUENTLY PERFORMED. CONSTITUTIONAL KARYOTYPING SHOWED A NORMAL MALE KARYOTYPE (46,XY). WHOLE-EXOME SEQUENCING IDENTIFIED A PATHOGENIC MISSENSE VARIANT IN THE *EDA* GENE (NM_001399.5: c.467G>A;p.ARG156HIS) IN THE HEMIZYGOUS STATE. THE VARIANT WAS CONFIRMED BY SANGER SEQUENCING. SEGREGATION ANALYSIS DEMONSTRATED THAT THE PATIENT'S MOTHER WAS HETEROZYGOUS FOR THE SAME VARIANT. IN SILICO PREDICTION TOOLS SUPPORTED THE PATHOGENIC NATURE OF

THIS VARIANT, WITH A REVEL SCORE OF 0.54 AND A 3ONET SCORE OF 0.80. BASED ON THE CONCORDANT CLINICAL AND MOLECULAR FINDINGS, A DIAGNOSIS OF X-LINKED HYPOHIDROTIC ECTODERMAL DYSPLASIA (CHRIST-SIEMENS-TOURAINÉ SYNDROME) WAS ESTABLISHED. THE PATIENT WAS SUBSEQUENTLY ENROLLED IN A MULTIDISCIPLINARY FOLLOW-UP PROGRAM INVOLVING DERMATOLOGY, PEDIATRIC DENTISTRY, OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY, OPHTHALMOLOGY, PULMONOLOGY, NUTRITION, AND CHILD PSYCHIATRY.

Figure 1 : (a) Typical facial features including protruding ears, full lips, a prominent forehead, and thin, sparse eyebrows and eyelashes, (b) fine hair with reduced density, (c) Conical teeth and hypodontia, (d) patient with dental prosthesis.

III. DISCUSSION

All In X-linked HED, hemizygous males typically present with severe and characteristic manifestations, whereas heterozygous females are often mildly affected or clinically asymptomatic. This phenotypic variability among female carriers is largely explained by X-chromosome inactivation, an epigenetic mechanism ensuring dosage compensation between the sexes [3].

In the present family, the heterozygous mother exhibited an unexpectedly severe phenotype, involving dental agenesis, hair abnormalities, and nail dystrophy. Such clinical expression contrasts with the usually subtle manifestations reported in female carriers of *EDA* pathogenic variants and strongly suggests skewed X-chromosome inactivation, with preferential inactivation of the normal allele in ectoderm-derived tissues [4]. Previous studies have demonstrated that skewed X-chromosome inactivation in carriers of X-linked HED can result in significant clinical involvement, occasionally approaching the severity observed in affected males. This phenomenon may be tissue-specific and contributes substantially to the wide heterogeneity of ectodermal manifestations observed among female carriers [5]. The clinical and molecular characterization of the *EDA* c.467G>A (p.Arg156His) variant in this family further expands the genotypic and phenotypic spectrum of X-linked hypohidrotic ectodermal dysplasia. A better understanding of genotype-phenotype correlations, particularly the role of X-chromosome inactivation, is essential for accurate diagnosis, prognostic

assessment, optimized multidisciplinary care, and appropriate genetic counseling [2].

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